

Packing simulation applied to thermoplastic composite wastes

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Content

- Context
- Manufacturing process description
- Numerical simulation
- Descriptors of packing
- Perspectives

Context

Current composite recycling routes

and bottlenecks

Processes for recycling thermoplastic composites

- Economic viability ?
- Lower mechanical properties
- Uncertainty of properties

→ Lack of models to understand and optimize recycling processes

Manufacturing process description

Study case : Thermosaïc® pilot line

Recycling cycle : CoDiCoFRP

Final product
/ End of life

Shredding

Discontinuous
chips

Stamping

Recycled
panel

Thermosaic®

Current bottlenecks

Input

Material
(Discontinuous
chips made of
continuous
fibers)

Geometry and position can vary

Thermosaic® Process

Black box with many variables, with
uncertain link between input and
output

Output

Mechanical
properties

Global stiffness and strength

Objectives

Objectives

The descriptors have two purposes :

Random stack

2. Establish a direct link

Mechanical properties
of consolidated panels

1. Provide a compact and discriminating description

Objectives

Input

Material

Influence of the entrance material on the stack

Define descriptors of packing

Rearrangement of the stack under "low temperature" press

Track evolution of descriptors

Rearrangement of the stack under "high temperature" press

Track evolution of descriptors

Consolidated microstructure of processed panel

Mechanical properties

Output

Objectives of today's presentation

Input

Material

Influence of the
entrance material
on the stack

Define descriptors
of packing

Mechanical
properties

Output

Numerical simulation

PyBullet : open source library

- Python interface of Bullet Physics server
- Real time contact detection
- Multi-physics simulation
- Often used in robotics, machine learning ...

→ Adaptation from fiber* to chips deposition

*Forró, C. et al. (2020). Visualizing and analyzing 3D metal nanowire networks for stretchable electronics. *Advanced Theory and Simulations*, 3(8), 2000038

Generation of numerical stacks with PyBullet

- **Input :**

- Chip data (position, orientation, geometry, mass ...) **20 mm square chips simplification and mono-material**
- Environment data (gravity, deposition area ...), **number of deposition steps**

- **Output :**

- Position, orientation of chips
- List of generated contacts during packing

Descriptors of packing

Classification of contacts

270 chips on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of chips : 20 mm * 20 mm * 2 mm

1 surface of contact

1 line of contact

2 points
of contact

Classification of contacts

270 chips on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of chips : 20 mm * 20 mm * 2 mm

- ≈ 2 contacts for each chip \rightarrow stability of the stack
- Densification can be tracked with an increase of number of contacts

Through-thickness chips detection

270 chips on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of chips : 20 mm * 20 mm * 2 mm

- Mapping of chip surface density
- Indicator of local lack or excess of chips

Level dispersion

270 chips on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of chips : 20 mm * 20 mm * 2 mm

- Evaluation of the filling rate of each layer
- Link with the volume fraction of the stack

Effect of aspect ratio on descriptors

270 chips on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of chips : 20 mm * 20 mm * 2 mm

270 chips on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of chips : 10 mm * 40 mm * 2 mm

- Aspect ratio 1:1 for squares and 1:4 for rectangles
- Iso volume per chip (conservation of thickness and surface)

Effect of aspect ratio on descriptors

270 chips on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of chips : 20 mm * 20 mm * 2 mm

270 chips on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of chips : 10 mm * 40 mm * 2 mm

Effect of aspect ratio on descriptors

Number of element among each layer

- Lower layer filling rate for rectangles in “low layers”
 - Increase of the number of layers for rectangles
- Lower volume fraction for rectangles

Perspectives

Theoretical validation

270 “fibers” on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of fibers : 1 mm * 25 mm

Comparison to analytical models using
identical aspect ratio (1:25)

Experimental validation

270 chips on a 150 mm * 150 mm deposition square
Size of chips : 20 mm * 20 mm * 2 mm

High speed camera, 1000 images per second

Identify numerical parameters of gravity, friction and bounces to fit experimental behavior

Future work

Input

Material

Influence of the entrance material on the stack

Define descriptors of packing

Rearrangement of the stack under "low temperature" press

Track evolution of descriptors

Rearrangement of the stack under "high temperature" press

Track evolution of descriptors

Consolidated microstructure of processed panel

Mechanical properties

Output

Contour Plot
Displacement(Z)
Analysis system
0.000E+00
Local Max = 0.000E+00
Node 20891
Local Min = 0.000E+00
Node 20891

Thank you for your attention Any questions?

Awen Bruneau – ICCM23

Workshop CoDiCoFRP

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Appendices

Overlapping

Strand size: 6 mm x 3 mm

6 mm

Failure follows the path with the shortest overlaps

Industrial impacts

Industrial impacts

Composite manufacturers,
Recycling companies

Thermosaic®
pilot line

Customization

Sell recycled panels

Customers

Investments in upgrading
the feeding line

Composite
manufacturers

Ensure reliability and controlled
mechanical properties